

Knowledge of Nutrition on the Growth and Development of Children in Zaria Local Government Area, Kaduna State

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Abstract

The study was motivated by the need to provide adequate nutrients in food necessary for the growth and development of children in Zaria Local Government Area, Kaduna State. Three (3) research questions were raised and analyzed for the study. Survey research was adopted for the study. The population of the study consisted of one thousand (1000) primary six (6) pupils in five public primary schools. Stratified Proportionate Sampling Technique was used to select a sample size of one hundred (100) pupils from the population. The instrument used for data collection was a structured questionnaire with a total number of 30 items titled "Nutritional Knowledge, Attitudes and Practices Questionnaire" (NKAAPQ) which was administered in each of the five selected schools. Descriptive statistics was used to analyze the data. The result on nutritional knowledge showed that the function of protein-rich foods is to build the body muscles with mean score of 4.02. The result on the nutrition attitudes of primary school pupils revealed that pupils preferred taking meat to vegetables and do not worry about the kind of food eaten (M=4.05) and 3.95 respectively. School lessons on nutrition (4.05), eating breakfast before going to school (3.95) and taking money to school (3.50) were identified as the major nutrition practices of primary school pupils. The study concluded that pupils had adequate theoretical knowledge on nutrition, however, the practical aspects of applying nutrition knowledge were very poor. The study recommended that parents and care givers should play a vital role in shaping children's nutrition attitudes and practices at an early stage. Also modeling healthy nutrition behavior that children will grow with it into adulthood by parents and significant others.

Key words: Nutrition, Growth, Development, Children, Nutrients.

Introduction

Nutrition is the process whereby cellular organelles, cells, tissues, organs, and the body acquire and use essential food substances to keep structural and functional integrity of the body (Nicola, 2012). Growth is the increase in size of an individual due to increase in number and size of the cells, resulting in an overall increase (Morre and Mollenhauer, 2009). Development refers to the qualitative and quantitative changes and acquisition of numerous competences for optimal functioning in a social milieu (Pratima, 2012). Growth and development entail unique characteristics of children and any hindrances in this process at any stage

can possibly result in aberration of growth and development (Arun, Shailaja and Rao, 2015). Nutrients act as substrates in all the metabolic reactions in cells necessary for the growth, development, function, and maintenance of body structure (Gibney, Lanham-New, Cassidy and Vorster, 2009). Child malnutrition can be as a result of inadequate nutrients in food (under-nutrition) or the excessive consumption of certain nutrients in food (over-nutrition). One of the major health challenges of children specifically in developing countries like Nigeria is under-nutrition (Ozoka, 2018). According to Jimoh, Anyiam and Yakubu

(2018), malnutrition has been identified as a major factor responsible for developmental challenges in children, such as deficits in cognitive skills, motor skills, social behavior, and school achievement.

Obijiofor, Ikpala, Nnani and Nwakile (2020) states that nutrition is very vital during the formative age of life and has a substantial impact on the physical, mental, health status of children and of productivity as adults. For optimal growth and development in children to be achieved, the diet must contain essential nutrients to support growth processes. Oguizu and Okafor (2019) argued that nutrition awareness at an early stage helps establish a foundation for healthy eating habits that the child can apply throughout life. Nutrition education is the key factor in improving the nutritional knowledge, attitude and practices of school children, families, and the community (Velma, 2012). The child's family environment including parental knowledge on nutrition can make healthful diets more available and accessible to children at homes, such as encouraging breakfast consumption, avoiding junk food intake and modeling of healthy food behaviors which can be achieved through the knowledge of nutrition education (Harris, 2012).

Mamba, Napoles and Nwaka (2019) observed that nutrition education planned at an early age is more likely to have a long-term positive influence on children nutrition problems such as child obesity, under nutrition and nutritional deficiency. Oldewage-Theron and Egal (2010) revealed that food consumption pattern of children is strongly associated with foods that are available and accessible in the environment. Most children of low-income families believed that nutritious food especially those with high protein content are expensive and only the rich can afford such nutritious meals (Velma, 2012). Proteins perform numerous functions in the body such as tissue repairing, building of muscles, organ function and maintenance of health and well-being. Inappropriate intake of proteins can have paramount consequences for tissue and organ function, health maintenance as

well as individual total well-being, (Ozoka, 2018).

Mundia (2012) stated that nutrition practices such as breakfast before school, knowledge on nutrition and preference for junk foods instead of a proper lunch correlates with the fact that unhealthy snacks are common nutrition practices prevalent among school children. Nutrition plays a vital role in determining the growth and development of children. This study is carried out to assess the influence of nutrition on the growth and development of children in Zaria Local Government Area, Kaduna State.

Statement of the Problem

Children who eat poorly are more likely to develop certain long-term health problems and complications (Oguizu and Okafor, 2019). The consumption of food high in sugar, salt and fat during childhood can increase the risk of health challenges in adulthood. The researcher observed that most of the food items consumed by primary school children are from sugar based, high carbohydrates and fat. There is need for adequate nutrition knowledge for healthy growth and development in children. School children's own knowledge level of nutrition has not been of primary research concern probably because they seem to be dependent on parents' nutrition knowledge, habits and preferences. The target has always been on the knowledge of caregivers as well as parents that are responsible for feeding children. It is therefore important to examine the nutrition knowledge help establish a foundation for healthy nutrition attitudes and practices those children. Thus, the need to conduct the study on nutrition knowledge on the growth and development of children in Zaria Local Government Area, Kaduna State.

Objectives of the Study

The study was on the knowledge of nutrition on the growth and development of children in Zaria Local government Area of Kaduna State. The specific objectives are:

1. assess the nutritional knowledge of

- primary school pupils on growth and development in Zaria Local Government Area, Kaduna State.
- 2. examine the nutrition attitude of primary school pupils on growth and development in Zaria Local Government Area, Kaduna State.
- 3. examine the nutrition practices of primary school pupils on growth and development in Zaria Local Government Area, Kaduna State.

Methodology

Research Design

A survey research design was adopted for this study. Adi (2019) posits that survey research design seeks to obtain information that discloses existing phenomenon by asking individuals about the perceptions, opinions, attitudes, practices and behavior or beliefs on a field of research interest. The research design was deemed appropriate because the researcher elicit data from the respondents on their nutrition knowledge, attitude, and practices.

Study Area

The research was conducted in five public primary schools selected in Zaria city, Tukur Tukur, Gyellesu, Kwarabai and Tudunwada wards of Zaria Local Government Area, Kaduna State. Zaria Local Government is a commercial city and doubles as the area headquarters with thirteen wards in Kaduna State, which is located in north-central Nigeria. Zaria Local Government consists of 117 public primary schools. The total number of pupils in 2018/2019 academic session is estimated to be over one hundred and twenty-five thousand, seven hundred and twenty pupils (125,720) (Kaduna State ASC Report, 2018/2019).

Population of the Study

The study population comprised of primary six pupils in public primary schools in Zaria Local Government Area, Kaduna State. The target population of the study comprised of one thousand (1000) pupils from five public primary schools in Zaria city, Tukur Tukur,

Gyellesu, Kwarabai and Tudunwada wards of Zaria Local Government Area, Kaduna State. The list was collected from the school authorities.

Sampling and Sampling Technique

Stratified proportionate sampling technique was used to select one hundred (100) primary six pupils from five public primary schools in Zaria Local Government Area, Kaduna State which constituted the sample

size using the formula; $n(\frac{N}{p})$ where n (estimated sample size); P (Population); N (Strata) represent the number of pupils from each school.

$$N_1 P: 100(\frac{180}{1000}) = 18$$

$$N_2 P: 100(\frac{200}{1000}) = 20$$

$$N_3 P: 100(\frac{210}{1000}) = 21$$

$$N_4 P: 100(\frac{190}{1000}) = 19$$

$$N_5 P: 100(\frac{220}{1000}) = 22$$

$$\text{Sample} = 18+20+21+19+22 = 100$$

Instrument for Data Collection

The instrument used for data collection was the questionnaire titled, "Nutrition Knowledge, Attitude and Practices Questionnaire" (NKAAPQ). The instrument was adapted from the study of Mamba, Napoles and Nwaka (2019) and modified by the researcher to suit the research objectives. The instrument consisted of thirty (30) items questionnaire on a four (4) point scale of preference distributed as Strongly Disagree (SD-1), Disagree (D-2), Agreed (A-3) and Strongly Agree (SA-4).

NKAAPQ comprised of four (4) sections A-D, Section A sought for information on demographic characteristics of the respondents; section B-D addressed the objectives of the study. The instrument was subjected to face and content validity to assess the appropriateness to measure specific objectives. The researcher with the

help of three research assistants visited each of the schools where the questionnaire was administered and retrieved.

Method of Data Analysis

Data from the study were analyzed using descriptive statistics of percentages, frequency counts, means and standard deviation. A score mean of 2.5 was used as the benchmark, therefore any mean response that has mean rating of 2.5 or above was considered agreed and any item that has a

mean rating of less than 2.5 was considered as disagreed.

Results and Discussion

The results of the study are presented on table 1-3. Results from the study of nutrition knowledge of primary school pupils revealed that respondents had knowledge on nutrition and its functions in the body, nine (9) items all agreed to the nutrition knowledge of the respondents with only one item disagreed.

Table 1: Mean Rating of respondents on Nutritional Knowledge of Primary School Pupils (N=100)

S/N	ITEMS	SD	D	A	SA	X	Std	Remarks
1	Breakfast is the most important meal of the day	10.0	10.0	20.0	60.0	3.3	23.8	Agreed
2	Different foods have different functions in the body	6.0	14.0	50.0	30.0	3.0	19.4	Agreed
3	At least six (6) glasses of water should be taken daily	4.0	6.0	40.0	50.0	3.4	23.5	Agreed
4	The main function of protein-rich foods is to build muscles	0.0	0.0	30.0	70.0	4.02	33.2	Agreed
5	The main function of starchy-rich foods is to provide energy	4.0	6.0	30.0	60.0	3.95	26.2	Agreed
6	The main function of dairy products is to build strong teeth/bones	2.0	8.0	22.0	68.0	3.6	29.9	Agreed
7	Foods (sugary foods such as sweet, food containing high amount of salt, processed foods and fats such as fried foods, oils) should be restricted	60.0	30.0	6.0	4.0	1.5	26.2	Disagreed
8	Lack of adequate nutrition knowledge can affect physical growth and maturation	6.0	4.0	40.0	50.0	3.3	23.5	Agreed
9	A balanced diet contains all the six classes of food	10.0	10.0	40.0	40.0	3.1	17.3	Agreed
10	Nutrition is the eating of good food for good health, proper growth and development	4.0	6.0	10.0	80.0	3.7	36.8	Agreed

Results from the study of nutrition attitude of primary school pupils showed that the respondents prefer meat to vegetables with a mean value of 4.05. the respondents agreed that all nutritious foods are expensive

(3.95), the respondents disagreed with fruits being healthy snacks (2.4). 7 items all agreed on the nutrition knowledge while, 3 items disagreed on the items listed.

Table 2: Mean Rating of Respondents on Nutrition Attitudes of Primary School Pupils N = 100

S/N	ITEMS	SD	D	A	SA	X	StD	Remarks
1	It is healthy to drink boiled water	20.0	40.0	20.0	20.0	2.4	10.0	Disagreed
2	We should eat varieties of foods as much as possible	40.0	30.0	14.0	16.0	2.1	12.3	Disagreed
3	Preference of meat to vegetables	70.0	20.0	6.0	4.0	4.05	30.8	Agreed
4	All nutritious foods are expensive	5.0	15.0	20.0	60.0	3.95	24.2	Agreed
5	The taste of food is more important to me than its nutrient content	2.0	8.0	24.0	56.0	3.1	24.2	Agreed
6	I do not have to worry about the kind of food because I am still young	6.0	4.0	40.0	50.0	3.90	23.5	Agreed
7	It is hard to practice nutrition knowledge at home.	0.0	0.0	50.0	50.0	3.5	28.9	Agreed
8	Eating healthy food is only important during illness	0.0	20.0	34.0	46.0	3.3	19.8	Agreed
9	Fruits are healthy snacks	60.0	30.0	0.0	10.0	1.6	26.5	Disagreed
10	Good feeding and hygiene are related	2.0	8.0	24.0	56.0	3.1	24.2	Agreed

Table 3 presents results on nutrition practices of primary school pupils. This revealed that the major nutrition practices

of respondents were eating breakfast every day before going to school and taking money to school with mean values of (4.0)

Table 3: Mean Rating of Respondents on Nutrition Practices of Primary School Pupils N = 100

S/N	Items	SD	D	A	SA	X	Std	Remarks
1	Have school lessons on nutrition	0.0	10.0	10.0	80.0	4.05	37.0	Agreed
2	Boil water before drinking	70.0	20.0	2.0	8.0	1.5	30.9	Disagreed
3	Eat breakfast every day before going to school	10.0	10.0	30.0	50.0	3.95	19.1	Agreed
4	Take money to school for snacks	2.0	8.0	30.0	60.0	3.50	26.3	Agreed
5	I choose what to eat	0.0	10.0	24.0	56.0	3.2	24.4	Agreed
6	Drink at least six (6) glasses of water every day	58.0	30.0	10.0	2.0	1.6	25.0	Disagreed
7	Carry a lunch box to school	50.0	40.0	10.0	0.0	1.6	23.8	Disagreed
8	The typical daily family meal consists of breakfast, lunch, and dinner	50.0	30.0	20.0	0.0	1.7	20.8	Disagreed
9	Wash hands before and after handling food, eating food, and visiting the toilet	40.0	36.0	22.0	2.0	1.9	17.2	Disagreed
10	Dispose home waste and refuse properly	30.0	30.0	10.0	30.0	2.4	10.0	Disagreed

Discussion on Findings

Table 1 revealed that majority of the respondents displayed knowledge on nutrition. The respondents were able to identify the various functions of food nutrients. This is because nutrition is being taught in schools. This result agrees with Ozoka (2018) that proteins have the functions of tissue repair, building of muscles, organ function and maintenance of health and well-being. Inappropriate intake of proteins in children diet can have adverse consequences for tissue and organ function, health maintenance and an individual total well-being. Mamba *et al* (2019) stated that carbohydrate is the most know food group providing the body with energy, knowledge of this information will enable school children choose appropriately. According to Obijiofor, Ikpala, Nnani and Nwakile (2020) nutrition of school children is very essential for during the formative age of life. It has a substantial impact on the physical and mental development, health status and of productivity as adults. Nutrition knowledge helps establish a foundation for healthy eating habits which can apply throughout life.

Table 2 showed findings on the nutrition attitude of primary school pupils. The nutrition attitude found children were preferring meat to vegetables, and the knowledge that nutritious foods are expensive mean values of 4.05, and 3.95 respectively. This is in accordance with Mamba *et al* (2019) who stated that the common nutrition attitude in children include the belief of nutritious foods being expensive, preference of meat to vegetables and the taste of food being more important than its nutrient content. Food consumption of primary school pupils is strongly associated with foods that are available and accessible in their environment. Oldewage-Theron and Egal, (2010) revealed that eating whatever is available is one of the issues associated with the attitude of children.

Table 3 revealed result on the nutrition practices of primary school pupils. Mundia (2012) posits that the nutrition practices common among children include taking

breakfast before going to school because breakfast is the most important meal of the day and preference of taking money to school in place of lunch boxes. The money taken to school is mostly used for sweets and unhealthy snacks otherwise known as junk foods. This alters the child's nutrition status as the intake of sweets and unhealthy snacks is found to be detrimental to the healthy growth and development of children. Nutrition can be taught to children in the school environment, during school meals, health, and nutrition clubs. The school is one of the major social contexts in which lifestyles are nurtured. The school fosters and alters nutrition knowledge, attitude and practices of children learnt from their various homes and communities (Velma, 2012).

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study looked at influence of nutrition on the growth and development of children in relation to knowledge on nutrition, nutrition attitude and nutrition practices. Pupils had adequate knowledge on nutrition, however, the practical aspects of applying this knowledge could be a challenge if not encouraged at home. Based on the findings, the study recommended that:

1. Parents and caregivers should play a major role in shaping children's nutrition attitude and practices at an early age by making nutritious food more available and accessible at home, avoiding junk foods, and modeling healthy food behaviors
2. School health policies should be enforced towards improving the school environment and making it favorable for pupils to make good food choices while in school.
3. Nutrition education should be a life-long learning and such that adapts according to the maturation age changes and nutrition requirement of the body. Nutrition education can be promoted in school, through the mass media, nutrition clubs and associations. At the family level, nutrition education can be promoted by healthy feeding, home grown

gardens and use of affordable healthy food items should be encouraged. The most expensive foods are not necessarily the best kinds of food, children need adequate diet with adequate amount of all the nutrients.

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